

Study of Serum-Ferritin Level in Stroke Patients and its Outcome in Patients Admitted in Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Stroke is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, with inflammation playing a pivotal role in its pathogenesis. Serum ferritin, an acute-phase reactant and marker of iron metabolism, is linked to oxidative stress and inflammation, potentially influencing stroke outcomes. Studying its levels may provide insights into prognosis and therapeutic targets in stroke management.

Aim and Objectives: To assess the level of serum ferritin in stroke patients admitted in tertiary care centre and to correlate the level of serum ferritin with the disease outcome in the patients.

Materials and Methods: This study was conducted as a prospective Observational Study on Patients admitted in medicine ICU, tertiary care hospital, Bhopal, during the study period of 18 months i.e. from 1st September 2022 to 29th February 2024. The clinical severity of stroke was assessed using Canadian Stroke Scale at the time of admission and on the 6th day of admission, the severity of stroke was re-assessed clinically using CSS and serum ferritin levels were again measured in all the subjects.

Results: Mean serum ferritin levels in patients with admitted with stroke at the time of admission was 276.30±155.52 ng/ml whereas that at day 6 was 301.95±228.86 ng/ml. 51 cases (31.9%) with stroke deteriorated over the hospital stay. Mean serum ferritin levels in deteriorated group was significantly higher as compared to non-deteriorated group ($p < 0.05$). Serum ferritin at day 6 to be good predictor of adverse outcome i.e. deterioration as per CSS (AUC=0.897; 95% CI-0.842-0.951; $p < 0.05$) and serum ferritin at admission was found to be fair predictor of adverse outcome (AUC=0.798; 95% CI- 0.723-0.873; $p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Serum ferritin levels are prognostic marker of severity of stroke as well as outcome in patients with stroke. Elevated serum ferritin is strongly positively correlated with early neurological deterioration in stroke patients. Elevated serum ferritin, a marker of iron stores, thus not only help in predicting short term and long term prognosis but signals the need for more intensive patient care and management protocols.

Keywords: Ferritin, Stroke, Ischemic Stroke, Correlation, Prognosis, Outcome.

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Introduction

Stroke, also called as cerebrovascular accident or brain attack is characterized by focal neurological deficit due to acute compromised cerebral perfusion secondary to vascular injury (infarction or hemorrhage). [1-3] Stroke is mainly of two major types, ischemic stroke and haemorrhagic stroke. World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that approximately 15 million people suffer from stroke globally. Out of the total burden of stroke, 87% cases are due to ischemic stroke and remaining 10-15% strokes are haemorrhagic strokes. [4,5] Stroke is the second leading cause of death Globally and

approximately four fifth of the deaths occur in low and middle countries. [6]

Inflammatory process plays a significant role in pathophysiology of stroke. Exposure to any insult due to injury or infection leads to production of acute phase proteins (APP) and these APP can be seen elevated in both acute as well as chronic inflammatory states. Various Acute phase reactants include ferritin, fibrinogen, hsCRP, haptoglobin, tumour necrosis factor (TNF) and complement factors (C3 and C4). [7]

Literature suggests that iron play an important role in the development of neurotoxicity as well as edema after the stroke. In cerebrovascular disease, reactive oxygen species (ROS) are accumulated as a result of oxidative stress or hypoxic acidosis, releasing ferritin stored in the cells as free iron. This reaction leads to catalysis of preformed radicals such as superoxide (O_2^-) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) into hydroxyl radical (OH) which is highly reactive and toxic, aggravating the damage. This ferrous iron mediated free radical mechanism is thought to play an important role in acute stroke.[8] This iron dependent concept of non-apoptotic cell death was termed as ferroptosis by Dixon in 2012, a condition different from autophagy, apoptosis and necrosis.[9]

Serum ferritin level is one of the prognostic markers that has attracted a lot of clinical interest recently. Serum ferritin was once thought to be solely a stress response to stroke; however it is currently being investigated as a marker of stroke prognosis.[10] Serum ferritin levels at the time of admission are associated with a poor prognosis, indicating that elevated body iron reserves prior to the onset of stroke may exacerbate the cytotoxicity of cerebral ischemia. Accordingly, it has been proposed that elevated serum ferritin affects the prognosis of ischemic stroke and, by increasing atherogenesis, serves as a risk factor for ischemic episodes.[11,12] With the above background, the present study was conducted at tertiary care centre to assess the level of serum ferritin in stroke patients admitted in tertiary care centre and to correlate the level of serum ferritin with the disease outcome in the patients.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted as a prospective Observational Study on Patients admitted in medicine ICU, Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College and associated Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh during the study period of 18 months i.e. from 1st September 2022 to 29th February 2024. Both males and females, aged ≥ 18 years, who presented within 48 hours of onset of symptoms of acute stroke, diagnosed on the basis of clinical examination and neuro-imaging (computed tomography/magnetic resonance imaging brain) were included whereas patients with recent infection, anaemia, liver failure, who received blood/blood component transfusion in the previous 7 days and who received thrombolysis were excluded from the study.

Sample size was estimated using the formula

$$n = \frac{z^2}{d^2} pq$$

where, $z=1.96$ at 95%CI, p =prevalence of ischemic stroke(0.15%),[5] $q=100-P(99.85\%)$, d =allowable error (0.5%). Based upon the formula, sample size was estimated to be 160.

After obtaining ethical clearance from Institute's ethical committee, all the patients fulfilling inclusion criteria were enrolled and written consent was obtained from them. Data regarding sociodemographic variables along with detailed history was obtained. All the patients were then subjected to general and systemic examination.

The clinical severity of stroke was assessed using Canadian Stroke Scale[13] at the time of admission.

Further, data regarding investigations such as CBC, ESR, PS comment, Serum ferritin, electrolytes, along with Chest Xray and CT or MRI brain was obtained from the case form.

On the 6th day of admission, the severity of stroke was re-assessed clinically using CSS and serum ferritin levels were again measured in all the subjects. The CSS scores at admission and on the 6th day were then be compared and the patients were categorized into two groups:

- "not deteriorated" group (patients in whom, over the course of 6 days, the CSS score increased or remained the same) and
- "deteriorated" group (patients in whom the CSS score decreased).

Statistical Analysis

Data was compiled using MsExcel and analysis was done using IBM SPSS software version 20. Categorical data was expressed as number and percentage whereas continuous data was expressed as mean and standard deviation. The mean admission-day and 6th-day serum ferritin levels were determined in each of these groups, and the comparison between the two groups ("not deteriorated" and "deteriorated") was then made using the Student's *t*-test. Correlation of serum ferritin with CSS was done using Pearson correlation coefficient. ROC curve analysis was done to assess the predicting ability of serum ferritin for adverse outcome. P value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

This study was conducted on a total 160 cases admitted with stroke. Mean age of patients enrolled in our study was 60.30 ± 11.93 years and about 77.5% cases were males.

Figure 1: Distribution of cases according to serum ferritin levels in patients with stroke

Mean serum ferritin levels in patients with admitted with stroke at the time of admission was 276.30 ± 155.52 ng/ml whereas that at day 6 was 301.95 ± 228.86 ng/ml (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Distribution according outcome based on Canadian Stroke Scale

Mean Canadian Stroke Scale score at admission was 5.191 ± 2.205 , which increased slightly to 5.681 ± 3.12 and the mean change in CSS was 0.49 ± 0.915 . As per the Canadian Stroke Scale, 51 cases (31.9%) with stroke deteriorated over the hospital stay (Figure 2).

Table 1: Association of serum ferritin levels with outcome

Serum ferritin	Not deteriorated		Deteriorated		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
At admission	240.05	135.74	353.79	167.72	0.001
At day 6	204.20	152.87	510.86	225.25	0.001

Mean serum ferritin levels in deteriorated group at admission as well as day 6 was significantly higher as compared to non deteriorated group ($p < 0.05$) (Table 1).

Table 2: Correlation of serum ferritin with Canadian stroke scale

Correlation		R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F	Sig.
Serum ferritin at admission with	CSS at admission	0.052	0.003	-0.004	2.209	0.430	0.513
	CSS at day 6	0.319	0.102	0.096	2.970	17.89	0.001
	CSS difference	0.426	0.182	0.176	2.367	35.05	0.001
Serum ferritin at day 6 with	CSS at admission	0.095	0.009	0.003	2.202	1.426	0.234
	CSS at day 6	0.442	0.195	0.190	2.811	38.37	0.001
	CSS difference	0.609	0.371	0.367	2.075	93.33	0.001

Our study found a strong positive correlation of serum ferritin level at day 6 with difference in Canadian stroke scale between admission and day 6 value (r=0.609; p<0.05) whereas we found a moderate positive correlation of serum ferritin level

at admission with CSS difference and serum ferritin level at day 6 with CSS at day 6 (r=0.40-0.599; p<0.05). Also we found a weak positive correlation of serum ferritin at admission with CSS at day 6 (r=0.319; p<0.05) (Table 2).

Table 3: ROC curve analysis of serum ferritin levels for predicting adverse outcome

Sr. Ferritin (ng/ml)	Area	Std. Error	P value	95% CI	Cut off	Sensitivity	Specificity
At admission	0.798	0.038	0.0001	0.723-0.873	275	82.4	68.8
At day 6	0.897	0.028	0.0001	0.842-0.951	275	96.1	80.7

In present study, ROC curve analysis revealed serum ferritin at day 6 to be good predictor of adverse outcome i.e. deterioration as per CSS (AUC=0.897; 95% CI-0.842-0.951; p<0.05) and serum ferritin at admission was found to be fair predictor of adverse outcome (AUC=0.798; 95% CI- 0.723-0.873; p<0.05). (Table 3, Figure 3).

Figure 3: ROC curve analysis of serum ferritin levels for predicting outcome

Discussion

This study evaluated serum ferritin levels in stroke patients admitted to a tertiary care center and examined its association with outcomes among them. The outcomes were analyzed using the Canadian Stroke Scale (CSS) and the correlation between serum ferritin levels and stroke severity was explored. The mean serum ferritin level at the

time of admission was 276.30±155.52 ng/ml, which increased to 301.95±228.86 ng/ml by day 6. These findings are in line with previous research suggesting that elevated serum ferritin levels are common in stroke patients and are indicative of an acute-phase response. For instance, Ranjan et al found that higher serum ferritin levels were associated with increased stroke severity and worse

clinical outcomes[14] Elevated ferritin levels reflect underlying inflammation and oxidative stress, which play critical roles in the pathophysiology of stroke. The observed increase in serum ferritin levels from admission to day 6 underscores the ongoing inflammatory response post-stroke, which can exacerbate neuronal injury and impair recovery. This pattern aligns with findings from Millerot et al who reported that elevated ferritin levels were associated with larger infarct volumes and poorer functional outcomes. [15]

The Canadian Stroke Scale (CSS) was used to assess stroke severity and outcomes in our study. The mean CSS score at admission was 5.191 ± 2.205 , which showed a slight increase to 5.681 ± 3.12 , indicating marginal improvement in neurological status. However, 31.9% of patients experienced deterioration during their hospital stay. This deterioration can be attributed to various factors, including the extent of the initial brain injury, secondary complications, and the inflammatory response. Côté et al validated the CSS as a reliable tool for assessing stroke severity and predicting patient prognosis.[16] In our study, the mean change in CSS was 0.49 ± 0.915 , indicating that while some patients showed improvement, a significant proportion either remained stable or worsened.

Our study demonstrates a significant association between elevated serum ferritin levels and poorer outcomes in stroke patients. Specifically, mean serum ferritin levels at admission were substantially higher in the deteriorated group (353.79 ± 167.72 ng/ml) compared to the non-deteriorated group (240.05 ± 135.74 ng/ml). This trend continued on day 6, with ferritin levels rising to 510.86 ± 225.25 ng/ml in the deteriorated group versus 204.20 ± 152.87 ng/ml in the non-deteriorated group. These findings indicate that higher ferritin levels correlate with a greater risk of clinical deterioration during hospitalization. Elevated serum ferritin is a marker of increased iron stores and systemic inflammation, both of which are known to exacerbate brain injury following a stroke. The role of ferritin as a predictor of stroke outcomes has been investigated in previous studies [17,18] For instance, DeGregorio-Rocasolano et al found that patients with higher serum ferritin levels had larger infarct volumes and poorer neurological outcomes. This aligns with our observation that elevated ferritin levels at admission and day 6 are associated with worse clinical progression. [19]

The significant difference in serum ferritin levels between the deteriorated and non-deteriorated groups in our study ($p < 0.05$) underscores the importance of monitoring ferritin levels in stroke patients. High ferritin levels at admission and their

increase over time could help clinicians identify patients at higher risk of deterioration, enabling more tailored and aggressive management strategies. Mohan et al also documented prognosis of the patient to be positively linked with the serum ferritin level. When compared to those who improved, those who declined had higher serum ferritin levels, and this difference was statistically significant. [20] Khan et al reported significant association between elevated serum ferritin levels and severe stroke, as well as unfavorable outcomes. [21]

Our study observed a significant correlation between serum ferritin levels and stroke outcomes, as measured by the Canadian Stroke Scale (CSS). Specifically, we found a strong positive correlation between serum ferritin levels on day 6 and the change in CSS from admission to day 6 ($r = 0.609$; $p < 0.05$). Additionally, there was a moderate positive correlation between serum ferritin levels at admission and the change in CSS, as well as between serum ferritin levels on day 6 and CSS at day 6 ($r = 0.40-0.599$; $p < 0.05$). A weak positive correlation was also noted between serum ferritin levels at admission and CSS at day 6 ($r = 0.319$; $p < 0.05$).

Millerot et al, reported that higher serum ferritin levels were associated with greater stroke severity and poorer outcomes, highlighting the role of ferritin as an indicator of the inflammatory response in stroke. [15] This aligns with our observation that higher ferritin levels correlate with more significant changes in CSS, reflecting greater neurological impairment and slower recovery. Elevated serum ferritin levels signify an acute-phase response, which includes increased inflammation and oxidative stress, both of which are critical in stroke pathology. Sultana et al [22] found that elevated ferritin levels in stroke patients were linked to worse functional outcomes, which supports our findings of a moderate to strong correlation between ferritin levels and changes in CSS scores. This suggests that ferritin can be a useful biomarker for predicting stroke recovery trajectories. The weak positive correlation between serum ferritin levels at admission and CSS at day 6 might be due to various factors influencing stroke outcomes, such as secondary complications, individual variations in inflammatory responses, and the effectiveness of medical interventions. Nonetheless, the presence of any positive correlation highlights the potential of ferritin as an early marker of prognosis.

The ROC curve analysis conducted in our study revealed that serum ferritin levels serve as valuable predictors of adverse outcomes in stroke patients. Specifically, serum ferritin levels on day 6 were identified as a good predictor of deterioration, as assessed by the Canadian Stroke Scale (CSS), with

an AUC of 0.897 (95% CI: 0.842-0.951; $p < 0.05$). Similarly, serum ferritin levels at admission were found to be a fair predictor of adverse outcomes, with an AUC of 0.798 (95% CI: 0.723-0.873; $p < 0.05$). These findings highlight the potential utility of serum ferritin as a prognostic biomarker in stroke management. Elevated ferritin levels reflect underlying inflammation and oxidative stress, both of which are implicated in the pathophysiology of stroke and subsequent neurological deterioration. He et al found that higher serum ferritin levels were associated with worse clinical outcomes in patients with acute ischemic stroke. [23] Their findings support our observation that elevated ferritin levels are indicative of a heightened inflammatory response and are predictive of adverse outcomes. Garg et al findings were also consistent with our study that Serum ferritin levels are correlated with the prognosis of the illness and have a substantial positive link ($P < 0.001$) with the severity of acute ischemic stroke. [24] This suggests that serum ferritin could serve as a reliable biomarker for identifying patients at higher risk of deterioration, enabling clinicians to implement timely interventions to mitigate adverse outcomes.

The sensitivity and specificity analyses further underscore the predictive accuracy of serum ferritin levels in identifying patients at risk of deterioration. At a cutoff of 275 ng/ml, serum ferritin levels on day 6 demonstrated a high sensitivity of 96.1% and specificity of 80.7%. Similarly, serum ferritin levels at admission exhibited a sensitivity of 82.4% and a specificity of 68.8%. These findings indicate that serum ferritin levels, particularly on day 6 post-admission, can effectively discriminate between patients who are likely to experience clinical deterioration and those who are not.

Our study had certain limitations. Serum ferritin was assessed in patients with stroke, however, other factors which might affect the serum ferritin levels and other iron studies could not be done. Second, the study was conducted as a unicentric study and sample size was small and thus the findings could not be generalized.

Conclusions

Serum ferritin levels are prognostic marker of severity of stroke as well as outcome in patients with stroke. Elevated serum ferritin is strongly positively correlated with early neurological deterioration in stroke patients. Elevated serum ferritin, a marker of iron stores, thus not only help in predicting short term and long term prognosis but signals the need for more intensive patient care and management protocols.

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